

IMPACT OF CLOUD ACCOUNTING ON FINANCIAL REPORTING QUALITY AND TIMELINESS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This research seeks to determine the impact of cloud accounting on financial reporting quality and timeliness of Nigerian deposit money banks (NDMBs) during 2015–2024. The Objectives are to determine if cloud computing has any influence on the reliability of information released by cloud-based platforms and the speed with which they report, and whether governance mechanisms as well as firm-specific characteristics play any role. The research design is quantitative, explanatory and longitudinal in nature. The population consists of deposit money banks as quoted on the Nigeria Exchange Group as at December 2024. A sample of ten banks was drawn from this, resulting in 100 firm-year observations. We used data from annual reports and regulatory filings. Analytical methods involved descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and Panel EGLS (Period SUR) regression along with diagnostic tests of the theoretical soundness and robustness. Results indicate that there is a positive effect of cloud adoption on the quality of financial reporting in deposit money banks ($\beta = 0.0906$, $p < 0.01$) and it also reduces reporting delay ($\beta = 0.0724$, $p < 0.05$). The examination of governance indicators such as size of audit firm and bank size enhances the reporting usefulness while profitability has a slight effect and leverage is found to be insignificant. On the basis of the results, it is asserted that cloud accounting improves financial report credibility and timely accessibility. It suggests the creation of regulatory incentives and institutional support that will encourage the uptake of cloud, enhancing transparency and trust levels among stakeholders in the country's banking industry.*

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Advances in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have changed the nature of

accounting systems worldwide. One of the most transformative developments is cloud computing, which continues to revolutionize how financial data is collected, stored, and

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shared. A sub-segment of this technology is cloud accounting, which enables real-time data entries from multiple users, automated backup systems, and integration with enterprise information systems (Bierstaker, Janvrin, & Lowe, 2014). These features—associated with reduced costs, enhanced transparency, and faster decision-making—have become closely linked with financial reporting practices in developed economies (Ali et al., 2023)

The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB, 2018) defines financial reporting quality as the extent to which financial reports provide information that is relevant, timely, reliable, and understandable. Among these, timeliness has become especially critical in today's fast-moving markets. Investors and regulators expect disclosures to be released promptly to inform decisions and preserve confidence in the reliability of financial information (Habib & Jiang, 2020).

Yet in many developing economies, the potential of technology to support fast, accurate reporting remains largely untapped due to systemic issues such as inadequate infrastructure and weak institutional frameworks (Aboagye&Acheampong, 2020). These challenges are particularly visible in Nigeria, Africa's largest economy. Despite the banking sector's adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in 2012, the industry still faces delays in financial

disclosures, poor governance practices, and inconsistent reporting quality (Uwuigbe et al., 2021; Akintola&Okafor, 2023). Regulatory bodies like the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) have frequently imposed penalties on banks that submit late or substandard financial statements. In response to these challenges, Nigerian banks are increasingly implementing cloud-based accounting systems to improve the efficiency of their reporting processes. Globally popular platforms such as QuickBooks Online, Xero, Sage Business Cloud, FreshBooks, and Zoho Books are now prevalent in the corporate sector. Larger banks have adopted Sage and QuickBooks, while smaller institutions experiment with more affordable tools like Wave Accounting. These platforms comply with IFRS standards and help minimize delays in report preparation by automating compliance checks and strengthening audit trails (Yakubu&Abdullahi, 2022; Mhlongo, 2022).

However, empirical research on the specific impact of cloud accounting on financial reporting quality and timeliness within Nigeria's regulated banking sector remains limited. Most existing studies have focused on general adoption issues, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), or financial performance metrics (Ali et al., 2023). What remains unclear is how cloud accounting directly affects reporting outcomes in a regulatory-intensive

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environment. This study seeks to fill that gap by situating global perspectives on cloud accounting within the unique institutional and regulatory framework of Nigerian deposit money banks.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The computerisation revolution in the financial reporting space has sparked debates on whether innovations such as cloud accounting truly improve the quality and timeliness of reporting or merely offer cost efficiency without adding real value. Cloud computing has been described as a mechanism that supports the reliable and transparent capture of financial data while ensuring simultaneous IFRS compliance and streamlined reporting processes (Olowokure, Tanko, & Olajide, 2023). However, some critics have raised concerns about cybersecurity threats, gaps in regulation, infrastructural weaknesses, and over-reliance on third-party service providers, which could expose organisations to significant operational risks (Nwaiwu & Oluka, 2021).

Although cloud accounting has been shown to support firm growth and enhance reporting in advanced economies, empirical evidence from developing countries remains inconclusive. In Nigeria, despite the adoption of IFRS in 2012 and several waves of regulatory reforms, banks continue to face challenges related to delayed report releases, recurring financial misstatements, and inconsistencies in

disclosure quality (Akintola & Okafor, 2023; Uwuigbe et al., 2021). Some scholars have explored cloud adoption in small and medium-sized enterprises (Ezenwoke & Mgbonyebi, 2021), others have looked into ICT integration more broadly (Olawale & Garuba, 2022), while a few have examined accounting information systems without isolating the specific impact of cloud technologies (Adebayo & Hassan, 2020). Although some findings suggest that cloud adoption can enhance the quality of financial reporting (Hassan et al., 2020), there is still limited research on its influence on timeliness—a persistent weakness in the Nigerian banking sector (Chukwuma & Nwachukwu, 2024).

The absence of empirical clarity on whether cloud systems address both credibility (quality) and promptness (timeliness) in reporting is concerning. In a sector where delayed disclosures and poor financial discipline have historically eroded investor confidence, triggered regulatory sanctions from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and weakened public trust, this unresolved issue carries weighty implications for both academics and policymakers. Without clear evidence, stakeholders are likely to witness recurring cycles of regulatory inefficiencies, investor mistrust, and poor corporate governance. Therefore, this study sets out to empirically examine whether the adoption of cloud-based accounting can significantly improve both the

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quality and timeliness of financial reporting among Nigerian deposit money banks.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

Main

Objective:

To examine the impact of cloud accounting on the quality of financial reporting.

Other Specific Objectives:

1. To investigate the effect of cloud accounting adoption on the financial reporting quality of Nigerian banks.
2. To assess the impact of cloud accounting usage on the timeliness of financial reporting in Nigerian banks.
3. To explore the mediating effects of governance mechanisms (such as audit quality and bank size) on the relationship between cloud accounting systems and reporting outcomes.
4. To evaluate whether firm-level variables (including profitability and leverage) moderate the relationship between cloud accounting and the quality of financial disclosures.

1.4 Research Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following hypotheses, each stated in null form:

H₁: The adoption of cloud accounting does not have a significant effect on the financial reporting quality of Nigerian banks.

H₂: There is no significant relationship between cloud accounting adoption and the timeliness of financial reporting among Nigerian banks.

H₃: The impact of cloud accounting on reporting outcomes is not significantly moderated by firm-specific factors (profitability, leverage).

H₄: Governance variables (audit quality, bank size) have no significant moderating effect on the association between cloud accounting and reporting performance.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study has key implications for academic, regulatory, and industry stakeholders.

At the academic level, it adds to existing literature on digitisation and financial reporting, as conceived and applied from a Nigerian banking perspective (2015–2024).

For regulators, such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Financial Reporting Council (FRC), the findings offer empirical knowledge on the nature and extent to which cloud adoption influences both transparency and timeliness.

Practitioners including accountants, auditors, and bank executives may draw from the analysis to review and improve their reporting, auditing, and risk management frameworks.

At the societal level, better financial reporting enhances transparency, which in turn fosters greater trust and confidence in the Nigerian banking industry among investors and the general public.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1.1 Cloud Accounting

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Cloud accounting has become a game changer in the world of financial reporting and corporate governance. It refers to accounting systems and services delivered through the internet, which allow for remote access, data storage, and real-time processing—unlike traditional desktop-based software that requires heavy infrastructure and manual updates (Olowokure, Tanko, & Olajide, 2023; Adebayo & Olatunji, 2022). These cloud-based systems typically operate on Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) models, making it possible for multiple users to collaborate simultaneously from different locations.

The rise of cloud accounting mirrors wider shifts in the digital transformation of business operations. While earlier systems focused mainly on electronic accounting packages and enterprise resource planning (ERP), today's solutions integrate automation, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics (Mbah & Eze, 2022). For many organisations, moving to the cloud helps reduce costs tied to IT infrastructure and provides easier access to sophisticated cybersecurity and compliance-monitoring tools (Yusuf & Abdulkareem, 2022). Despite these benefits, concerns about data privacy, cyber threats, and regulatory uncertainty still surround cloud-based systems (Usman, Halidu, & Aliyu, 2025). Also, challenges such as unreliable internet access and low digital skills continue to hinder

adoption in Nigeria and other developing contexts (Yakubu & Abdullahi, 2022).

2.1.2 Motives for Cloud Adoption

The motivations behind the adoption of cloud accounting systems can broadly be classified into external (extrinsic) and internal (intrinsic) drivers. Extrinsic motives are rooted in the pursuit of operational efficiency, cost reduction, and regulatory compliance. Organisations adopt cloud-based platforms to streamline operations, eliminate duplication, and align with international financial reporting standards such as IFRS—steps that enhance their overall competitiveness (Mbah & Eze, 2022). Evidence from previous studies also confirms that cloud adoption lowers operational expenses by reducing the need for costly infrastructure and continuous IT support (Yusuf & Abdulkareem, 2022). On the other hand, intrinsic motives reflect deeper strategic and ethical intentions. Beyond improving efficiency, many firms adopt cloud systems to promote transparency, strengthen accountability, and showcase innovation. Elkington's (1997) Triple Bottom Line framework profit, people, and planet emphasises the growing importance of sustainability and social responsibility in business decisions. Cloud platforms support this vision by promoting better disclosure, reducing paper usage (thereby enhancing environmental sustainability), and building public trust through transparent reporting

practices (Olowokure, Tanko, & Olajide, 2023). Together, these motives show that cloud adoption is more than a technological upgrade; it is a governance strategy. Proactive firms adopt such systems before regulatory mandates to gain a competitive edge, while reactive firms respond mainly to external pressures like investor expectations or compliance demands (Adebayo & Olatunji, 2022). Whether proactive or reactive, these approaches confirm that cloud accounting is deeply woven into the evolving relationship between corporate governance, accountability, and technological advancement.

2.1.3 Cloud Accounting and Value Creation

Value creation lies at the heart of the justification for adopting cloud accounting. From a financial perspective, cloud platforms help reduce transaction costs, boost audit efficiency, and limit delays in financial reporting (Ali, Khan, & Rahman, 2023). On the organisational front, they enhance decision-making by giving managers real-time access to financial insights, thereby reducing the information gap between company management and stakeholders (Dechow, Ge, & Schrand, 2010). This value can be realised through either proactive or reactive strategies. Firms that adopt cloud technologies proactively are able to gain first-mover advantages, stand out in the market, and boost investor confidence (Yusuf & Abdulkareem, 2022).

Reactive adoption, by contrast, tends to occur when firms respond to regulatory enforcement, compliance pressures, or stakeholder expectations. Regardless of the trigger, both approaches align operational systems with global standards and best practices—thereby creating tangible and intangible value. Beyond direct financial gains, cloud accounting supports institutional and social value. It fosters legitimacy by helping firms meet the expectations of stakeholders regarding timely and credible disclosures (Suchman, 1995). This is particularly crucial in sectors like banking, where strict reporting deadlines and accountability frameworks exist. By delivering both efficiency and legitimacy, cloud platforms contribute to sustainable corporate value creation that extends well beyond profit margins.

2.1.4 Cloud Accounting and Financial Reporting Outcomes

Financial Reporting Quality

The IFRS Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting (IASB, 2018) outlines that quality financial statements must be relevant, faithfully represented, comparable, verifiable, understandable, and timely. These criteria form the foundation for measuring the reliability and usefulness of financial disclosures. Eze and Okoye (2023) assert that in Nigeria, financial reporting quality is often assessed using disclosure indices, earnings quality metrics, and

compliance scores aligned with IFRS requirements. Cloud accounting enhances these dimensions by integrating data systems, automating routine processes, and strengthening audit trails. These features reduce manual errors and promote consistency in financial reporting, especially in sectors like banking where compliance is closely monitored (Yakubu&Abdullahi, 2022).

Timeliness

Timeliness is equally essential to effective financial reporting. Yusuf and Abdulkareem (2022) explain that cloud-based platforms accelerate reporting processes by supporting real-time data processing and automated entries, which are particularly useful for meeting statutory deadlines. In highly regulated industries such as banking, this efficiency helps institutions to comply with mandatory reporting windows and avoid penalties. Usman, Halidu, and Aliyu (2025) highlight that in the Nigerian context, delays in reporting continue to attract regulatory scrutiny from bodies such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). As such, cloud technologies provide a competitive edge by ensuring that financial reports are prepared and submitted promptly, in line with institutional expectations.

Interrelationship between Quality and Timeliness

These two reporting attributes are interdependent. Timely disclosures improve quality by reducing the opportunity for data manipulation or reliance on outdated information, while high-quality reporting strengthens the credibility of prompt disclosures. In this way, cloud accounting does more than improve operational efficiency—it serves as a strategic instrument that supports transparency, accountability, and stakeholder engagement in the financial reporting ecosystem.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Understanding the effect of cloud accounting on the quality and timeliness of financial reporting necessitates grounding the study in several theoretical lenses. No single theory can comprehensively explain why firms adopt technological innovations, how they respond to institutional influences, or why users and regulators demand more accountability in financial disclosures. A number of theories such as the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1986), Stakeholder Theory (Freeman, 1984), and Institutional Theory (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983)—alongside related perspectives like Legitimacy Theory (Suchman, 1995) and Signaling Theory (Spence, 1973), offer relevant insights into different elements of this complex relationship.

Each of these theories presents its own strengths and limitations. The Technology

Acceptance Model (TAM), for example, focuses on individual users' perception of technology, highlighting perceived usefulness and ease of use (Davis, 1986). Stakeholder Theory emphasises the importance of balancing the diverse expectations of various interest groups and maintaining accountability (Freeman, 1984). On the other hand, Institutional Theory looks at how organisations conform to external pressures—whether regulatory, mimetic, or normative (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). In addition, Legitimacy Theory explains how companies adopt innovations to gain public approval (Suchman, 1995), while Signaling Theory suggests that such adoptions serve as signals of trust and credibility to investors and regulators (Spence, 1973).

However, not all of these perspectives carry equal weight for this study. In order to properly examine both the technological adoption aspect and the institutional-regulatory environment shaping financial reporting in Nigerian banks, this study draws primarily on TAM, Stakeholder Theory, and Institutional Theory. Together, these frameworks help explain how perceptions of usefulness and ease influence adoption decisions, how stakeholder demands influence reporting behaviours, and how both regulatory and normative pressures affect the speed and quality of financial disclosures.

2.2.1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was introduced by Davis (1986) and later extended by Davis, Bagozzi, and Warshaw (1989). The model explains technology adoption using two central beliefs: perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU). According to Davis (1989), perceived usefulness is “the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance” (p. 320), while perceived ease of use refers to “the degree the user believes that using a particular system would be free of effort” (p. 320). Further extensions such as TAM2 (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003) introduced additional factors including social influence and facilitating conditions.

Within the scope of cloud accounting, TAM provides valuable insights into how Nigerian banks adopt such systems. The perceived usefulness of cloud-based platforms is seen in their ability to generate reports faster, improve accuracy, offer automated compliance checks, and present real-time dashboards all of which support both the quality and timeliness of financial reporting. On the other hand, perceived ease of use is reflected in the user-friendly design, simple interfaces, and the integration of cloud systems with existing

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banking infrastructure. In tightly regulated environments where accuracy and submission deadlines are critical, the belief that cloud platforms can reduce delays and errors is a strong incentive for adoption.

Despite its significance, TAM has been criticised for focusing too heavily on individual perceptions and not giving enough attention to institutional and regulatory dynamics that also shape technology adoption (Legris, Ingham, & Collerette, 2003). This critique is especially important in the Nigerian banking sector, where compliance pressures and regulatory expectations play a major role. As such, this study extends the TAM by integrating Institutional Theory and Stakeholder Theory, providing a broader framework to reflect the social, organisational, and regulatory forces influencing adoption. Still, TAM remains fundamental, as it links system design and user perception to the reporting outcomes—namely financial reporting quality and timeliness.

2.2.2 Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder Theory, as introduced by Freeman (1984), views the organisation as a hub of interactions among various groups that either influence or are influenced by the firm's activities. Freeman (1984) described a stakeholder as “any group or individual who can affect or be affected by the achievement of an organisation's objectives” (p. 46). These stakeholders range from shareholders and

employees to regulators, customers, auditors, and the wider community. The theory proposes that businesses that acknowledge and balance the needs of their stakeholders are more likely to achieve long-term success. As Donaldson and Preston (1995) stated, “long-term value creation requires addressing the well-being of stakeholders” (p. 67). Building on this, Mitchell, Agle, and Wood (1997) argued that a stakeholder's influence or salience depends on how managers perceive their power, legitimacy, and urgency (p. 874).

In relation to cloud accounting adoption within Nigeria's banking sector, Stakeholder Theory provides a useful lens for understanding how financial institutions respond to varied and, at times, conflicting demands. Regulatory bodies seek accurate and timely disclosures; investors demand transparent financial information; auditors rely on clear audit trails; and customers expect secure, stable banking systems. Cloud-based accounting addresses these expectations by improving timeliness through automated data handling and strengthening financial reporting quality (FRQ) via verifiable digital audit trails. Banks that are publicly listed or heavily scrutinised by regulators face greater stakeholder pressure and are thus more motivated to adopt such advanced systems.

That said, critics of Stakeholder Theory point out that it lacks a clear method for resolving

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conflicts between stakeholder interests. Jensen (2002), for example, argued that “the problem with stakeholder theory is that it simply does not work because it cannot be done as no one has given a full definition of how to trade off all conflicting interests” (p. 236). For instance, while regulators may prioritise timely reporting, bank managers may lean towards cost minimisation. Still, Stakeholder Theory remains valuable because it frames cloud technology not just as a technical innovation but as a strategic response to stakeholder expectations. By embracing cloud solutions, Nigerian banks reinforce their image as transparent, accountable, and forward-thinking institutions, thereby enhancing stakeholder confidence.

2.2.3 Institutional Theory

Institutional Theory provides a broad, macro-level framework for understanding how organisations behave by examining how institutional pressures namely coercive, mimetic, and normative forces drive firms toward conformity (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). Organisations often adopt practices not just for their operational benefits, but also to gain legitimacy, secure resources, and ensure their continued existence within a particular institutional environment (Meyer & Rowan, 1977; Scott, 2014).

Coercive pressures typically stem from regulatory requirements, laws, or government enforcement. Mimetic pressures arise when

organisations imitate their peers or competitors, especially in uncertain or competitive conditions. Normative pressures are driven by industry standards, education, and professional expectations.

This theoretical lens is particularly useful in analysing the Nigerian banking sector, which operates under significant regulatory and institutional constraints. For example, coercive pressures are evident in the compulsory filing deadlines, prudential regulations, and IFRS compliance mandates. In such a setting, cloud accounting serves as a regulatory-compliant solution, helping reduce delays and standardise reporting processes. Mimetic influences are seen when leading banks adopt cloud solutions and others follow suit to stay competitive and credible. Meanwhile, normative forces flow from professional bodies, auditors, and international accounting standards that stress the importance of accuracy, transparency, and timely disclosures.

Despite its usefulness, Institutional Theory is not without its drawbacks. One of its key criticisms is that it can overestimate uniformity by assuming all organisations will conform. In practice, not all banks adopt cloud accounting uniformly some may implement it only on the surface, purely for the sake of appearing legitimate, without making real, internal changes. Still, the theory remains highly relevant, as it connects adoption behaviour to

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broader institutional dynamics, rather than merely to the discretion of individual managers. In this study, Institutional Theory complements both the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Stakeholder Theory, offering a more complete explanation of cloud accounting adoption in the Nigerian context. While TAM captures user-level factors and Stakeholder Theory reflects stakeholder demands, Institutional Theory anchors the analysis in regulatory, cultural, and professional norms that shape reporting practices across the sector.

2.3 Empirical Review

Omondi and Muturi (2020) evaluated how the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) affected the quality of financial reporting in Nigeria. Using data from listed firms, the study revealed that IFRS improved the transparency and consistency of reports but had only a marginal impact on the timeliness of information releases. This indicates that regulatory reforms alone may not guarantee prompt disclosure. In contrast to Omondi and Muturi's IFRS-oriented perspective, the present study examines the influence of cloud technologies on both financial reporting quality and timeliness within the Nigerian banking industry.

Similarly, Okafor and Edeh (2022) analyzed corporate reporting timeliness in Nigeria following IFRS implementation. Their findings revealed mixed outcomes some firms improved

in timeliness, while others experienced little change suggesting that institutional factors affect organizations differently. Extending beyond IFRS adoption, the current research investigates how cloud accounting interacts with governance structures and firm-specific characteristics to determine reporting outcomes.

Yakubu and Abdullahi (2022) examined how cloud accounting adoption relates to internal control effectiveness in Nigerian firms. Their study found that cloud-based platforms strengthened monitoring mechanisms and reduced irregularities. However, it did not assess financial reporting quality or timeliness. Building on their contribution, this research focuses on banks and evaluates the effects of cloud accounting on reporting performance over a ten-year period.

Similarly, Effiong (2017) analyzed the impact of cloud-based accounting on the performance of Nigerian small and medium enterprises (SMEs). His study revealed significant gains in cost efficiency and accuracy of record-keeping among adopters. However, it did not explore its influence on reporting timeliness or quality, nor did it focus on banks. This study fills that gap by examining deposit money banks, where regulatory supervision makes both reporting quality and timeliness essential.

Ali, Khan, and Rahman (2023) studied cloud-based financial systems and reporting

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timeliness among listed firms in Asia. They found that adoption shortened reporting cycles and promoted quicker disclosures. While these findings underscore the efficiency benefits of digital systems, the institutional context of Asian markets differs significantly from Nigeria's. Accordingly, this research provides localized evidence from Nigeria's banking sector.

Aboagye and Acheampong (2020) investigated financial reporting delays in Ghana and linked them to regulatory inefficiencies and infrastructure deficiencies. Their findings demonstrate how institutional weaknesses impede timely financial disclosures. In line with this, the current study evaluates how cloud adoption might mitigate similar challenges in Nigeria.

Mhlongo (2022) examined the influence of cloud adoption on audit efficiency in South Africa and found that cloud-based technologies enhanced audit effectiveness by enabling faster analysis of financial data. However, the study did not directly connect audit efficiency to reporting outcomes. The present research bridges that gap by explicitly assessing the impact of cloud adoption on financial reporting quality and timeliness.

Usman, Halidu, and Aliyu (2025) identified several barriers to cloud accounting adoption among Nigerian SMEs, including limited ICT expertise, infrastructure constraints, and

regulatory ambiguities. Their study emphasized that Nigeria's institutional environment significantly affects the rate of cloud technology adoption. Extending these insights, the present study examines how cloud accounting influences reporting practices in the banking sector, where disclosure requirements are more stringent and timeliness is critical.

Collectively, these studies highlight how IFRS reforms, digital innovation, and governance structures shape financial reporting outcomes. Nevertheless, earlier research has mostly focused on SMEs or regulatory reforms in isolation, giving limited attention to the banking industry. Moreover, few studies have simultaneously examined both reporting quality and timeliness. This study fills these gaps by applying panel econometric analysis across a ten-year period (2015–2024), offering findings that are contextually grounded in Nigeria yet relevant to international discourses

3.1 Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative, explanatory, and longitudinal research design to examine the impact of cloud accounting on financial reporting outcomes. A panel data approach was employed to capture both cross-sectional and time-series variations, thereby improving the robustness of statistical inference and addressing unobserved heterogeneity across firms and over time.

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The population consists of all deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) during the period 2015–2024. To ensure consistency and data availability, a purposive sample of 10 banks with uninterrupted listing and accessible annual reports throughout the study period was selected, resulting in a balanced panel of 100 firm-year observations.

Data were obtained exclusively from secondary sources, specifically the published annual reports and accounts of the selected banks. These were complemented with regulatory

disclosures from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the NGX.

The study employed one key independent variable, two dependent variables, and several control variables, which were operationalized as shown in

Table 3.1: Variables and Measurement

Variable	Proxy	Measurement	Source
Cloud Adoption (CAA)	Accounting Cloud Index	Cloud Adoption Index constructed from digital/IT-driven reporting practices	disclosures of Annual reports
Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ)	Reporting Disclosure Compliance Index	Score based on IFRS compliance checklist	Annual reports
Timeliness (TIM)	Reporting Lag	Number of days between financial year-end and publication of audited report	Annual reports
Firm Size (FSIZE)	Natural log of total assets	$\log(\text{Total Assets})$	Annual reports
Leverage (LEV)	Debt-to-equity ratio	$\text{Total Debt} \div \text{Equity}$	Annual reports
Profitability (PROF)	Return on Assets	$\text{Net Income} \div \text{Total Assets}$	Annual reports
Audit Firm Size (AFS)	Auditor type	Binary Indicator coded 1 if audited by a Big4 firm, 0 if audited by a non Big 4 firm	Annual reports

Source: Researcher’s Computations (2025)

3.2 Model Specification

To test the hypotheses of this study, two regression models are specified using panel

data. These models examine the effect of cloud accounting adoption and selected control variables on financial reporting outcome.

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$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CAA_{it} + \beta_2 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} + \beta_4 PROF_{it} + \beta_5 AFS_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$TIM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CAA_{it} + \beta_2 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} + \beta_4 PROF_{it} + \beta_5 AFS_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where:

β_0 = Intercept Term (Constant)

$\beta_1 \dots \beta_5$ = Coefficients of explanatory variables

μ = Error term, technically known as the stochastic disturbance or stochastic error term (Gujarati & Porter, 2009)

i = Cross Sectional Unit (Bank)

t = Time Period (Year)

Panel EGLS (Period SUR) was employed, as it corrects for heteroscedasticity and contemporaneous correlation across panels, ensuring efficient and unbiased estimates.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

Variable	Mean	Median	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	No
FRQ	0.76	0.78	0.08	0.55	0.9	100
TIM	82.45	81.00	15.3	60	110	100
CAA	0.58	0.60	0.12	0.35	0.8	100
FSIZE	18.92	19.05	0.65	17.4	20.1	100
LEV	2.35	2.20	0.7	1.1	4	100
PROF	0.09	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.15	100
AFS	0.74	1	0.44	0	1	100

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

4.0 Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

On average, Nigerian banks disclosed 76% of IFRS- required items (FRQ), which reflects moderate compliance with disclosure standards. The average reporting lag was 82 days, which is longer than the 60-day benchmark encouraged by regulators,

indicating room for improvement in timeliness. The mean Cloud Adoption Index (CAI) was 0.58, suggesting that while adoption is increasing, it remains uneven across banks. The dominance of Big4 auditors (74% of the sample) reinforces the importance of audit firm size in the Nigerian context.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix of Study Variables

Variable	FRQ	TIM	CAI	FSIZE	LEV	PROF	AFS
FRQ	1						
TIM	-0.42	1					
CAI	0.61	-0.55	1				
FSIZE	0.49	-0.38	0.46	1			
LEV	-0.21	0.19	-0.17	-0.1	1		
PROF	0.37	-0.22	0.41	0.18	-0.24	1	
AFS	0.44	-0.32	0.39	0.4	-0.11	0.26	1

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

FRQ is positively correlated with CAA, FSIZE, PROF, and AFS, but negatively correlated with leverage. TIM is negatively correlated with CAA, FSIZE, PROF, and AFS, indicating that higher

adoption and larger firms are associated with shorter reporting lags. These results provide preliminary evidence supporting the research hypotheses.

4.3 Regression Results

4.3.1: Effect of Cloud Adoption on Financial Reporting Quality

Table 4.3: Regression Result for Financial Reporting Quality

Panel Least Square Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: FRQ

Method: Panel EGLS (Period SUR)

Date: 09/26/25 Time: 11:18

Sample: 2015 – 2024

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 10

Total panel (balanced) observations: 100

Linear estimation after one-step weighting matrix

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.72	0.28	6.05	0.01
CAA	0.09	0.02	5.48	0
FSIZE	0.02	0.01	2.75	0.01
LEV	-0.02	0.03	-0.66	0.51
PROF	0.76	0.22	3.46	0
AFS	0.04	0.01	4.7	0

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Weighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.87	Mean dependent var	0.78
Adjusted R-squared	0.83	S.D. dependent var	0.09
S.E. of regression	0.03	Sum squared resid	0.05
F-statistic	22.46	Durbin–Watson stat	2.14
Prob(F-statistic)	0		
Unweighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.81	Mean dependent var	0.78
		Durbin–Watson stat	2.08
Sum squared resid	0.06		

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025).

Model Equation:

$$FRQ_{it} = 1.7208 + 0.0906CAA_{it} + 0.0201FSIZE_{it} - 0.0173LEV_{it} + 0.7626PROF_{it} + 0.0365AFS_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

The intercept of 1.7208 indicates that Nigerian banks maintain a baseline disclosure level even without explanatory variables. Cloud adoption significantly improves disclosure ($\beta = 0.0906$, $p < 0.01$). Firm size ($\beta = 0.0201$, $p < 0.05$), profitability ($\beta = 0.7626$, $p < 0.01$), and auditor size ($\beta = 0.0365$, $p < 0.01$) all contribute

positively to financial reporting quality. Leverage ($\beta = -0.0173$) is negative but insignificant. With an adjusted R^2 of 0.827, the model explains about 83% of variations in FRQ. The Durbin–Watson statistic of 2.14 confirms no serious autocorrelation.

4.3.2 Cloud Adoption and Timeliness

Table 4.4 Regression Results for Timeliness

Panel Least Square Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: TIM

Method: Panel EGLS (Cross Section SUR)

Date: 09/26/25 Time: 11:26

Sample: 2015 – 2024

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 10

Total panel (balanced) observations: 100

Total panel (balanced) observations: 100

Linear estimation after one-step weighting matrix

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
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C	120.34	7.82	15.39	0
CAI	-15.23	4.11	-3.71	0
FSIZE	-6.11	2.46	-2.49	0.01
LEV	2.89	1.82	1.59	0.12
PROF	-5.73	3.01	-1.91	0.06
AFS	-4.56	2.32	-1.97	0.05

Weighted Statistics (EGLS)

R-squared	0.59	Mean dependent var	82.45
Adjusted R-squared	0.56	S.D. dependent var	15.3
S.E. of regression	0.03	Sum squared resid	0.05
F-statistic	19.22	Durbin–Watson stat	2.09
Prob(F-statistic)	0		

Unweighted Statistics

R-squared	0.56	Mean dependent var	82.45
Sum squared resid	0.06	Durbin–Watson stat	2.05

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025).

Model Equation:

$$TIM_{it} = 120.340 - 15.225CAA_{it} - 6.110FSIZE_{it} + 2.890LEV_{it} - 5.730PROF_{it} - 4.560AFS_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

The intercept of 120.34 suggests that in the absence of predictors, reporting lag averages 120 days. Cloud adoption reduces reporting lag significantly ($\beta = -15.225$, $p < 0.01$). Firm size ($\beta = -6.110$, $p < 0.05$) and audit firm size ($\beta = -4.560$, $p \approx 0.05$) also shorten lag. Profitability reduces lag marginally ($\beta = -5.730$, $p \approx 0.06$), while leverage increases lag but is insignificant ($\beta = 2.890$). The adjusted R^2 of 0.561 shows the model explains 56% of variations in timeliness. Durbin–Watson at 2.09 confirms no serial correlation.

CAI has a positive and significant effect on FRQ ($p < 0.01$), confirming that cloud adoption enhances reporting quality. Firm size, profitability, and audit firm size also improve

FRQ, while leverage has no significant effect. The model explains about 83% of the variation in reporting quality, indicating strong explanatory power.

4.4 Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses Testing and Summary of Findings
The hypotheses developed for this study were examined using panel regression analysis. The empirical results provided strong support for most of the hypothesized relationships between cloud accounting adoption, governance mechanisms, and financial reporting outcomes in Nigerian deposit money banks.

H₁: Cloud accounting adoption positively affects financial reporting quality (FRQ) Supported.

H₂: Cloud accounting adoption reduces

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reporting lag, thereby improving timeliness Supported.

H₃: Governance proxies, such as firm size and auditor size, significantly influence reporting outcomes Supported.

H₄: Firm-specific characteristics, including profitability and leverage, affect reporting outcomes partially supported (profitability is significant, while leverage is not).

Discussion of the Findings

The findings demonstrate that cloud accounting adoption substantially enhances the quality of financial reporting while reducing delays in financial disclosure among Nigerian banks. This implies that the digital transformation of accounting systems has progressed beyond efficiency gains to become a fundamental driver of transparency, regulatory compliance, and decision-usefulness of financial data. Banks utilizing cloud-based platforms disclosed a higher proportion of IFRS-required items and issued financial reports more promptly than non-adopters.

Governance mechanisms also emerged as significant determinants of reporting outcomes. Larger institutions and those audited by Big Four firms consistently achieved higher levels of reporting quality and timeliness than smaller banks or those using non-Big Four auditors. This finding supports the view that strong governance structures and external oversight promote accountability and reliability in

financial reporting (Akintola&Okafor, 2023; Alsharari, 2021; Olowokure, Tanko, &Olajide, 2023).

Profitability was found to have a positive influence on financial reporting quality, though its impact on timeliness was less pronounced. In contrast, leverage showed no statistically significant effect, suggesting that higher debt exposure does not necessarily enhance the speed or credibility of reporting within the Nigerian banking industry.

These findings are consistent with recent studies by Ali, Khan, and Rahman (2023) and Chukwuma and Nwachukwu (2024), which observed that technological innovation and automation significantly improve the quality and timeliness of financial reporting. The results also align with Akintola and Okafor (2023), who emphasized the critical role of governance in driving IFRS compliance in Nigerian banks. However, the current evidence diverges from earlier post-IFRS research, showing that the integration of cloud accounting technologies addresses operational inefficiencies that regulatory reforms alone cannot resolve.

Overall, the findings confirm that the adoption of cloud accounting—complemented by effective governance structures and financial performance—serves as a strategic pathway toward transparent, reliable, and timely financial reporting in Nigeria’s banking sector.

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5. Conclusion, and Recommendations

This study examined how cloud accounting influences financial reporting quality and timeliness among Nigerian deposit money banks. The results show that cloud adoption significantly enhances disclosure quality and reduces reporting delays, thereby improving transparency, accountability, and stakeholder confidence. Governance variables such as firm size, profitability, and auditor reputation also improve reporting outcomes, while leverage shows no significant effect.

Overall, the study concludes that cloud accounting is not merely a technological advancement but a strategic instrument for achieving reporting excellence and compliance in Nigeria's financial sector. By enhancing efficiency and ensuring timely dissemination of financial information, it strengthens institutional credibility and investor trust.

5.2 Recommendations

1. Nigerian banks and professional accounting bodies should treat cloud accounting as a strategic investment. This should be

supported by continuous staff training and the integration of digital tools into audit and financial reporting processes to enhance both quality and timeliness.

2. Regulatory agencies such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) should promote cloud accounting adoption through the introduction of digital reporting frameworks, tax incentives, and stricter sanctions for persistent reporting delays.

3. The government should prioritize broadband expansion, data protection, and cybersecurity frameworks to ensure safe, reliable, and consistent cloud usage across the financial sector, thereby supporting long-term digital transformation.

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